

POST-IMPACT FATIGUE BEHAVIOR OF CFRP LAMINATES FOR MARINE USE

Isao Kimpara and Koji Yamaguchi

*Advanced Materials Science R & D Center
Kanazawa Institute of Technology
3-1 Yatsukaho, Matto, Ishikawa 924-0838, Japan*

SUMMARY: The damage tolerance performance was comparatively evaluated in terms of CAI strength and damage progression under tension–compression fatigue loading based on the same coupon specimen level in CFRP woven fabric laminates for marine use. The concerned materials are T300 plain woven fabric, / vinyl-ester based on resin transfer molding (RTM). Fatigue tests were conducted on impact damaged coupon specimens of CFRP laminates with two damage levels for BVD (barely visible damage) and NVD (non visible damage) under three levels of maximum stress, 75 %, 65 % and 55 % of CAI strength, at a frequency of 5 Hz and stress ratio of $R=-1$. The impact damage and its growth behavior of CFRP laminates were successfully monitored using thermo elastic stress analyzer (TESA) and ultrasonic C-scan. It was clarified that the images of damage area were apparently different between the C-scan and the TESA, but that the damage growth behavior was well monitored similarly either by the TESA image and the ultrasonic C-scan image. As the TESA image gives the sum of principal stresses at surface, it was shown that the damage growth behavior was well observed by the “in-situ” damage imaging. The apparent stress relaxation at surface in the TESA image was successfully simulated by a FEM damage model in which delamination and crack are simultaneously combined.

KEYWORDS: Woven fabric CFRP, Impact damage, Post-impact fatigue, NDE facilities

INTRODUCTION

There has been a big technological gap between aerospace and marine composite materials not only in reinforcing fibers and matrix but also in manufacturing process. Marine composite materials have so far been limited mainly to E glass fiber and unsaturated polyester resin based on cold curing contact molding process. The fiber form has also been limited mainly to thick woven fabric and chopped strand mat. The application of advanced composite materials in the marine industry has been limited to high-performance racing yachts, high-speed power boats and some surface effect ships because of the high material cost and the sophisticated manufacturing process. However there is now more than sufficient evidence to show that properly engineered advanced composite structures will produce a much lighter and much more durable large-scale marine vehicles by means of rational choice of structural concept and manufacturing process. We note that several developments have recently been done which might be able to give cost effective and affordable new type of reinforcements and core materials for marine composite structures based on resin transfer molding (RTM) process.

The damage tolerance performance is comparatively evaluated in terms of compressive strength after impact. The durability is evaluated for some selected material systems through damage process observation under repeated loading. A better understanding of the damage mechanisms is essential to establish a reliable criterion for predicting the effects of such impact damage on durability. Several experimental and analytical studies was conducted on residual compressive strength after impact [1-4]. The damage growth behavior was monitored using NDE equipments under fatigue loading [5, 6].

A new simplified and unified approach was proposed using a coupon specimen to characterize compressive residual strength of impact-damaged CFRP laminates on destructive and non-destructive basis[1]. Impact load is applied directly to a coupon specimen by employing a drop-weight impact test tower, and impact-damaged area of the specimen is measured by ultrasonic C-scan

method. After the impact test, compressive load was applied with a newly developed compression test fixture. Residual compressive strength is related to impact energy and damaged area. After the impact test, tension-compression cyclic loading (stress ratio: -1) is applied and impact damage growth behavior is observed using ultrasonic C-scan and thermo elastic stress analyzer (TESA).

NDE FACILITIES

1. Ultrasonic C-scan

For ultrasonic C-scan (TU-2000, Toray Techno Co., Ltd), the transmission medium is water. Specimens are placed in a bath of water and a combined emitter and receiver piezoelectric transducer is also submerged and scanned over the specimen surface. Ultrasonic pulses are retransmitted through the specimen and detected by the scanning head. As delamination prevents ultrasonic transmission, the C-scan produces an image showing the shape, size, location and depth of delamination. This system has a minimum spatial resolution of 0.03mm. Frequency of the transducer is 25MHz.

2. Thermo elastic stress analyzer (TESA)

Thermoelastic stress analysis relates instantaneous changes in a material's stress state to instantaneous changes in the material's temperature. The fundamental thermoelastic relationship between temperature and hydrostatic stress is given by

$$\Delta T = -(KT) \cdot \Delta \sigma_{KK} \quad (1)$$

where ΔT is the local change in specimen temperature, K is the thermoelastic constant, T is the specimen temperature and $\Delta \sigma_{KK}$ is the change in the stress tensor invariants.

In order to obtain an experimental measure of these changes, a low amplitude sinusoidal stress applied to the specimen. Schematic of relation between the thermal response and the applied cyclic stress is shown in Fig.1.

In this thermo elastic stress analyzer (JTG-8010, JEOL), maximum and minimum peak temperature are measured and accumulated respectively to improve S/N ratio and then temperature amplitude distribution pattern corresponding to the stress amplitude distribution is obtained as a difference between these peak temperature patterns. In this system, temperature pattern in area could be measured. This system is a minimum spatial resolution of 100mm and a temperature resolution of approximately 0.001 deg K.

Fig.1 Schematic image of principle of TESA

TEST SPECIMEN AND TEST METHOD

1. Test specimens

The above approach was applied to CFRP woven fabric laminates for marine use. A kind of test specimen, T300B-3K woven fabric / vinyl-ester resin (T300B/VE), as baseline material, has been obtained and evaluated. As these test specimens, consisting of 9 plies of woven fabric, were cured under room temperature in RTM process, it was found that the flexural strength of after cured test specimens was more stable and higher than

that of as-received one. For this reason, a half of the total test specimens were cured using a heat oven. The condition of after cure was determined as 150°C in 2 hours based on the results of storage modulus measured by dynamic visco-elasticity tests. The size of impact test and CAI test specimens were 150mm in length, 2mm in thickness and 50mm in width, as shown in Fig. 2 (a). And PIF test specimens were cut in 43mm of width, as shown in Fig. 2 (b), due to chucking using grip.

Fig. 2 A size of test specimen for CAI and PIF test

2. Test method

Impact test

A drop weight with a steel semi-spherical tip was used as an impacter. The weight of impacter was 1113.5g and the radius of the tip was 8 mm. The specimen was mounted between the supporting steel plates with cut-out hole of 15mm in radius, as shown in Fig.3 and is given impact energy directly using the impacter. Height were chosen as 6 levels including 0 (no damage), 5cm, 10cm, 20cm, 30cm and 40cm. Impact damage in specimen is obtained and characterized by ultrasonic C-scan method.

Static Compressive test

The fixture has no additional device to prevent buckling. Compressive load was applied for specimen under a constant displacement condition. Cross head speed was 0.6mm/min. Load, displacement and strain at 6 points were measured.

Tension-compression fatigue

Tests were conducted on impact damaged as-received coupon specimens of CFRP laminates with two damage levels for BVD (barely visible damage, impact energy: about 1J/mm) and NVD (non visible damage, impact energy: about 0.25J/mm) by a sinusoidal load signal at 5Hz and stress ratio of $R=-1$ using Shimazu Servopulser. Anti-buckling fixture was not used. And, 3 kinds of maximum load were chosen: 75%, 65% and 55% of CAI strength. The damage growth was monitored using TESA, and ultrasonic C-scan at several intervals. Measurement items were load, deflection and strain at 4 points.

Fig.3 Schematic image of a fixture for impact test

RESULT

1. Impact test

Figure 4 shows a cross section of damaged area using a microscope. It was observed that matrix cracks occurred at the impact point and that matrix cracks occurred in large numbers at the bottom side than at the upper side. However, no matrix crack was observed far from the impact point. It was found that delamination tend to extent along longitudinal fibers. A long delamination was observed near the center of test specimen.

Fig. 4 A cross section of impact damaged test specimen

Figure 5 shows ultrasonic C-scan images and B-scan image of impact damage area at upper, center and bottom. The form of impact damage area was a cross at the

(a) Near impact side

(b) Center

(c) Opposite impact side

Fig. 5 Ultrasonic C-scan images of damaged test specimen (impact energy: 1.5J/mm)

(a) Projected damage area

(b) Accumulated damage area

Fig. 6. Relation between impact energy and damaged area of test specimens

upper of test specimen. And the form of impacted damaged area was a circle at the bottom of test specimen. At the center of this test specimen, it was combination between a small cross and a circle.

Impact damaged area of as-received test specimen at each interlayer was more scattered than that of test specimen with after curing, as shown in Fig. 6 (a). Accumulated damage area was defined as the total of impact damage area at each interlayer. Accumulated damage area of as-received test specimen was bigger than that of test specimen with after curing, as shown in Fig. 6 (b).

2. Static compressive strength after impact

CAI strength of as-received test specimens was more decreased than that of after cured test specimen as shown in Fig. 7 (a). However it was shown that CAI strength of all test specimens was in unique linear correlation with accumulated damaged area, as shown in Fig. 7 (b).

Fig. 8 Comparison about damage monitoring using between TESA and ultrasonic C-scan

3. Tension-compression fatigue strength

The in-situ damage imaging was able to be obtained using TESA. Figure 8 shows that initial damage of BVD test specimen and NVD test specimen were evaluated using ultrasonic C-scan and TESA. The forms of damaged area of BVD test specimen were different between ultrasonic C-scan image and TESA image. The damaged area of BVD test specimen could be observed using NDE facilities, while the damage area of NVD test specimen could not be observed using TESA, which could be observed using ultrasonic C-scan.

Impact damage growth was not observed for NVD test specimen at all load levels and BVD test specimen at lowest load level of 55% CAI strength. However, impact damage was observed to grow at middle and high load level of 65% and 75% CAI strength leading to a final failure of test specimens.

Table I Test matrix for PIF behavior

Initial impact energy (J/mm)	Load level (MPa)	% CAI strength	Number of cycles	Impact induced damage growth
0.25 (NVD)	77	55%	1000000 over	No
0.25 (NVD)	91	65%	1000000 over	No
0.25 (NVD)	105	75%	1000000 over	No
1 (BVD)	93	55%	1000000 over	No
1 (BVD)	111	65%	816467	Yes
1 (BVD)	128	75%	23043	Yes

TESA images of BVD test specimen at middle load levels at intervals were shown in Fig. 9. From

Fig. 9 Damage growth beh.

$N=3.0 \times 10^5$, no stress area occurred at center point of test specimen. Stress was degraded in load direction of impact damage point from $N=3.0 \times 10^5$ to $N=4.0 \times 10^5$. From $N=4.0 \times 10^5$ to $N=4.7 \times 10^5$, this phenomena was obvious. From $N=6.6 \times 10^5$, no stress area was increased in width direction of test specimen and stress was degraded in load direction of impact damage point.

Photo images of BVD test specimen after final failure were shown in Fig. 10. Crack paths were different on impact side and back side were different. From this result, it was obvious that crack did not propagate in the thickness direction of test specimen. Also, crack path was not linear at surface was not linear. Broken vertical strands of woven fabric were linked, resulting in formation of crack path.

Fig. 10 Face at impact side and back side of failure BVD test specimen

DISCUSSION

1. Initial impact damage

No stress area at the center of test specimen could be observed using TESA. One of the reason is that delamination between a vertical strand and a horizontal strand occurred and stress was not transferred through a horizontal strand.

2. Damage growth

In fatigue life of BVD test specimen at middle stress level, three regions could be distinguished: one is from initial to $N=4.0 \times 10^5$, two is from $N=4.0 \times 10^5$ to $N=8.0 \times 10^5$ and last is from $N=8.0 \times 10^5$ to final failure.

1) In the first region, delamination between plies near impact point was increased. At initial the form of delamination near impact side due to impact energy was cross. Delamination near impact side was extended and the form was transformed into circle.

2) In the second region, stress relaxation was observed in load direction of impact damage point. This is because micro buckling of vertical strands at impact point occurred. This phenomenon was discussed using FEM. A quarter of test specimen (25mm x 25mm x 2mm) was modeled using 3D-8nodes elements. Form of element was a cube in 0.5mm. It was assumed that delaminations in 7.5mm x 7.5mm existed between each layers. Four kinds of crack pattern were prepared, as shown in Fig. 11. Distribution of sum of principle stress of four kinds model was shown in Fig. 12. The deeper crack propagated in direction of thickness, the higher stress was degraded in load direction of impact point.

3) In the third region, micro buckling occurred near vertical strands and damaged area was propagated in the width direction of test specimen. As a result, final failure occurred due to degradation of effective cross section.

Fig. 11 Four kinds of finite element model

Fig. 12 Distinguish of sum of principle stress about four crack patterns

CONCLUSION

The ultrasonic B scope and C scope image of impact damaged regions enabled us to characterize and measure damaged area at each interlayer. It was also shown that accumulated damaged area of as-received test specimen was bigger than that of after cured test specimen at all impact energy levels. CAI strength of all test specimen showed a rough correlation to accumulated damaged area which was defined as the total of damaged area in each interlayer. Growth behavior of impact damage was observed using TESA and ultrasonic C-scan. In fatigue life, three regions could be distinguished. The apparent stress relaxation at surface in the TESA image was successfully simulated using a FEM damage model in which delamination and crack are simultaneously combined.

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